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ABSTRACTS

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Nano drugs: An approach towards effective medication

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Abstract: Biocompatibility and acceptability are the two most significant challenges for any drug delivery method as synthetic materials interact quite differently with human body cells than biological ones do. Using large-scale materials for drug delivery presents several challenges, including inadequate body absorption, low bioavailability and solubility, in vivo instability, target-specific delivery concerns, tonic effectiveness problems, and potentially hazardous side effects. By using nanostructures and nanophases in various scientific fields, particularly in nanomedicine and nano-based drug delivery systems, where such particles are of great interest nanotechnology has been discovered to bridge the gap between the physical and biological sciences. The knowledge and techniques of nanoscience are applied to medical biology, disease prevention, and treatment in the rapidly emerging field of nanomedicine. It encourages the use of nanoscale materials for nanorobots, nanosensors for diagnostics, delivery, sensory functions, and actuating materials in living cells. Pharmaceutical compounds have been improved in terms of efficacy, safety, physicochemical characteristics, and pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic profile by the use of nano-drug systems. Functionalized nano-drug systems in particular can increase the bioavailability of oral medications and give longer half-lives for pharmaceuticals injected into specific organs. Because of this, nano-drug delivery systems have the potential to improve treatment compliance and clinical results by minimizing systemic adverse effects and increasing pharmacological effects while reducing the frequency of administration. It is anticipated that the use of nanotechnology in medicine, namely in medication delivery, will increase. This poster highlights the usefulness of nanoparticle medications for a range of medical conditions.

Keywords: Drug delivery, Bioavailability, Nanotechnology, Treatments, Nanoparticles

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